

UZBEKISTAN'S FOREIGN RELATIONS IN THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR (in the case of Bukhara region in 1991-1995)

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Annotation. On the eve of independence and in its early years, the situation became more complicated due to the market economy, fundamental reforms, especially the increase in prices and unemployment. Also, the end of the Treaty of the Union was causing more harm than good because of the lack of raw resources. If we summarize the work in the past period of 1991, the industrialists produced only 300 million soums of chemical products instead of 316 million soums (in 1991 monetary value). This was lower than the indicator of the same period in 1991.

Keywords: cooperation, company, technical school, construction, transport, enterprises

For example, from January to September 15, 1990, instead of 27,920 tons of nitron fiber, 27,144 tons of products were actually produced. As a result, this network industry suffered a loss of 2.5 million soums. For example, in 1991, the team of the artificial fiber production plant in the Russian city of Novocherkassk did not send 37.7 tons of “Methylpyrrolidone” compound, which was considered as raw material, to the chemical industry enterprise in the Bukhara region.

In exchange for giving a lot of ammonia, saltpeter, weak nitric acid to agricultural workers, they received alkali, itacic acid and tnomourevin dioxide. As a result, in order to further expand the cooperation with foreign countries, the managers of the chemical industry, where you worked, started exchanging products with Japan and France. Because the chemical industry was a big customer of mineral fertilizers. This was very useful in establishing cooperation relations in the field of chemical industry of Bukhara region. In addition, both ammonium nitrate and weak nitric acid produced in the region were fundamentally different from such fertilizers

produced abroad in terms of their effective and qualitative effects. Therefore, Western countries are the main buyers of these mineral fertilizers.

In addition to these, the chemical industry of Bukhara region tried to specialize in the production of consumer goods and thereby ensure the purity of the environment. In 1991, the regional industrial enterprise began to produce a large number of “KO-1” water purification chemicals, various head washing shampoos, “Diola” washing powder, and “Fenax” insect repellent. In addition, various sheaths are made from artificial fiber. This served the needs of the people.

In the early years of independence, the production company “Tong” was established in Bukhara region. However, a number of other industrial enterprises have left their own mark in the history of the light industry of the region. There is a reason for us to draw such a firm conclusion. He appeared like a morning star in the sky of the economy of Bukhara region, which is undergoing development. That's why the company was called “Tong”. Since 1992, a contract has been signed between the company and Bukhara Industrial Pedagogical Technical College.

The idea of training a highly qualified specialist-coach was at the heart of this enterprise initiative. The contract concluded with the company “Tong” was the same term for the team of the technical school, which trained personnel for seven regions of the republic and even for the neighboring state of Turkmenistan.

A building, labor force, and sewing machines were organized for the organization of workshops in the technical school. However, some of the sewing machines were brought by the company “Tong”. 15 experts and workers taught the students the process of working with technical equipment. As early as April 1992, the results of the work were visible, and at first there was a net profit of 200-300 thousand soums per month (in 1992 currency). Of course, the company also made a profit from this cooperation. Emboldened by the previous steps, both teams made a net profit of 1 million soums (in 1993 currency) in 1993.

In 1993, a small dyeing workshop was established based on equipment purchased from Germany for the cutting and sewing workshop. And in the large

building, a complex technological system was created, which was implemented for the first time in the history of the industry of Bukhara region, from the processing of cotton fibers to the production of ready-made products. And this system was launched in the second quarter of the same year. In November 1992 alone, students received 9 thousand soums of salary (in 1992 currency).

In the first half of 1992, the analysis of a number of other industrial enterprises in the Bukhara region shows that the volume of production decreased in 20 out of 38 types of products in the “Tong” industry. As a result, in 30 enterprises, or one in three, the total production volume (in 1992 monetary value) decreased from the amount of 218,800 soums. The regional graphite-gypsum combine was unable to fulfill its annual plans as it was unable to provide 3.5 thousand soums to the suppliers, and 3.4 thousand soums to the yarn-spinning production association.

In 1992, industrial products worth 7734.5 million soums were produced in Bukhara region in 11 months of this year. It was 104.1 percent compared to 1991 at comparable wholesale prices. Production of consumer goods increased by 12.7% compared to 1991. In addition, in 1992 there were 51 enterprises and organizations that were operating at a loss. Their total loss (in 1992 currency) exceeded 100,000 soums.

In the 11th month of 1992, it was found out that 67328.7 thousand soums worth of consumer goods were illegally exported from the Bukhara region by the customs officials. The distribution of these goods and products by types shows the following situation.

- Fruit products - 3553.6 thousand soums.
- Policy products - 232.8 thousand soums.
- Food products - 1289.7 thousand soums.
- Industrial products - 22313.2 thousand soums.
- Construction materials were in the amount of -36,209 thousand soms.

It should be noted that the above indicators do not cover all areas. In fact, these indicators were several times more. In total, 62,710,700 soums, including

29,630,000 soums of various goods and material assets, which were taken from entrepreneurs in the Bukhara region while leaving the Olot Customs post, were confiscated.

As a result of the analysis of the work of these enterprises in the Bukhara region, it was found that 95 out of 852 small enterprises, 23 out of 176 companies, and only one out of 57 private enterprises produced products necessary for public consumption. During 1992, they produced products worth 82,500 soums, which was equal to only 1% of the national consumer goods produced in Bukhara region.

Since 1993, a number of industrial enterprises, Bukhara Oil Refinery, Bukhara “Zardo'z” Joint Stock Company and “Bukhoroteks” Joint Stock Company have been established in the region, and have participated in economic spheres and relations with a number of countries. In particular, it is located 65 km south of the center of Bukhara region (city of Bukhara). Korovulbazar district began to play an important role in foreign relations.

Korovulbazar was established on January 12, 1993 in the territory of Bukhara region, the area is 2.2 thousand km², the population is 13.9 thousand people (2005). There is 1 city (Korovulbazar) and 3 rural communities (Bozachi, Jargoq, Navbahor) in the district. The district center is the city of Korovulbazar. There are about 30 industrial construction, transport, enterprises in Korovulbazar. In 1956, oil and gas fields were identified from this area.

Construction of an oil refinery began in the city in 1993, and the plant was put into operation on August 22, 1997. Almost 500 million dollars were spent on the construction of the plant to financially ensure the construction of the enterprise, and banks, companies and firms of foreign countries participated in the construction process. The financial support of “Chase Manhattan” (America), “Crédi commercial de France”, “Pariba” (France), Japanese and US exports import banks was used. To implement the technological part of the project, the participation of the French company “TEKNEP”, the Japanese company “Marubeni” and Je Gi Si was

organized. The Turkish company “Gama” and the builders of Uzbekistan performed the construction and assembly works together.

The measures being implemented to increase the volume of production of competitive products, modernization of production capacities, diversification of the main branches of industry on the basis of technical and technological renewal, that are export-oriented and substitute for imports are aimed at increasing the volume of industrial enterprises of Bukhara region and increasing the volume of exports and production of products that substitute for imported goods.

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